

Conformational correction in trans of CFTR-F508del using a prion-like template: a novel therapeutic strategy for cystic fibrosis

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1. INTRODUCTION

General context

Cystic fibrosis is the most common lethal autosomal recessive disease in Caucasian populations, caused by mutations in the CFTR gene. The F508del mutation, which is present in approximately 90% of patients, leads to a misfolding of the NBD1 domain, preventing the chloride channel from reaching the plasma membrane.

Problem

The misfolded CFTR-F508del protein is recognized by the ERAD system and is degraded by the proteasome via the ubiquitin ligases RNF5/RNF185, before reaching its functional destination.

Limitations of current treatments

Pharmacological correctors (Lumacaftor, Tezacaftor) partially stabilize muted NBD1 but act passively, by occupying hydrophobic pockets. Their efficiencies remain insufficient for several variants and they do not actively address the folding defect itself. A strategy capable of actively the native conformation on NBD1-F508del represents an unexplored complementary pathway.

Originality and objective

The originality of this approach lies in the repurposing of a fundamental biological mechanism — the trans-conformational propagation characteristic of prions — from the pathological domain to the therapeutic one. This idea emerges directly from the observation that the AGAAAAGA motif, in the context of the prion, does not only convert the molecule to which it is attached, but also, through physical contact, the surrounding PrPC molecules. It is this trans correction property that we propose to exploit.

This thesis aims to design a chimeric protein NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA capable of acting as a conformational template: by interacting with surrounding NBD1-F508del molecules, it would impose the correct folding on them, allowing them to escape proteasomal degradation and resume their function.

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1 The F508del mutation and CFTR degradation

- Intrinsic thermodynamic instability of NBD1-F508del: the F508 deletion disrupts a network of critical hydrophobic contacts, affecting in the first place inter-domain interactions and leads NBD1 kinetically trapped in a misfolded state (Lewis et al., 2004).
- ERAD pathway: recognition by Hsp70/CHIP, ubiquitination by RNF5/RNF185, proteasomal degradation (Riepe et al., 2024).
- Mechanism of class I correctors (VX-809): passive stabilization of mutant NBD1 by occupation of hydrophobic pockets, partial restoration of trafficking to the membrane — but without active correction of the folding defect.

2.2 The conformational conversion mechanism of prions

- PrPC (rich in α -helices) \rightarrow PrPSc (rich in β -sheets): conversion induced in trans by direct contact with a PrPSc molecule acting as a template — the conformation propagates from molecule to molecule (Hara & Sakaguchi, 2020).
- The N-terminal region undergoes a major conformational change during conversion, while α -helices 2 and 3 are conserved (Eghiaian et al., 2004).
- Role of the AGAAAAGA motif (residues 113–120): initiation of conversion via formation of a class 7 steric zipper, with antiparallel β -sheets and an inter-sheet distance of 5.0 Å (Cheng et al., 2011). This motif is the initial point of contact between the template and its target — it orchestrates the conformational transition in trans.
- Recent work (Gatdula et al., 2025) shows that conversion is strictly required for toxicity, and that mutations such as G126V block all propagation. This demonstrates that the conversion process is genetically controllable and relies on specific molecular interactions — opening the door to its therapeutic exploitation.

2.3 Mechanistic convergence

- Direct functional parallel: just as PrPSc imposes its conformation on PrPC in trans via the AGAAAAGA motif, a chimera NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA could impose the native conformation of NBD1 on surrounding NBD1-F508del molecules, exploiting the same conformational template logic — but this time in a therapeutic direction.
- Structural justification: NBD1-F508del is kinetically trapped in a misfolded state but thermodynamically accessible to correction — it does not lack the energy to fold correctly, but rather a template to guide that folding. The chimera provides precisely that template.
- Critical distinction: unlike PrPSc, which propagates a pathological conformation, the chimera NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA would propagate a native and functional conformation. The mechanism is identical; the outcome is reversed.
- Distinction from correctors: whereas correctors act passively on mutant NBD1, the chimera acts actively on NBD1-F508del in trans — this is correction through conformational information rather than steric occupancy.

3. RESEARCH QUESTION AND HYPOTHESIS

Hypothesis A chimeric protein NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA, co-expressed with CFTR-F508del, could act in trans as a conformational template: by physically interacting with NBD1-F508del via the AGAAAAGA motif, it would impose the native conformation on it,

allowing it to escape recognition by the ERAD system and proteasomal degradation, and to resume trafficking to the plasma membrane.

Main question

Is it possible to design a chimeric protein NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA that interacts with NBD1-F508del in trans, imposes a stable conformation on it, and restores partial CFTR maturation in a cellular context?

Success criteria

- Demonstrable physical interaction between the chimera and NBD1-F508del (co-immunoprecipitation or FRET)
- Measurable increase in the thermal stability of NBD1-F508del in vitro in the presence of the chimera ($\Delta T_m \geq 3^\circ\text{C}$ by DSF)
- Half-life of CFTR-F508del extended by at least 30% when co-expressed with the chimera
- Detectable appearance of the mature form (band C) on western blot
- Absence of pathological aggregation (low or absent Thioflavin T signal)

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Design and production of chimeras

- Prior structural analysis of wild-type and F508del NBD1 (PDB: 2BBT) to identify optimal insertion sites for the AGAAAAGA motif in wild-type NBD1:
 - RI loop (residues 405–436): exposed region, compatible with inter-molecular interaction
 - C-terminal end of NBD1: maximal surface accessibility
 - Regulatory loop (around residue 670): zone of flexibility
- Particular attention will be paid to the RI loop (405–436), whose surface exposure and flexibility make it the most promising candidate for trans interaction with NBD1-F508del.
- Construction of 3 to 4 chimeric variants NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA with distinct insertion sites, plus controls:
 - Negative control 1: mutated motif (AGAAAAGA → AAAAAAA)
 - Negative control 2: wild-type NBD1 alone without motif
- Expression in *E. coli* (pET system, BL21-DE3 strain), purification by affinity chromatography (His-tag) and gel filtration.

4.2 Validation of trans interaction (central experiment)

- In vitro pull-down: incubation of purified chimera with purified NBD1-F508del, detection of the interaction by western blot.
- DSF in the presence of the chimera: measurement of the ΔT_m of NBD1-F508del alone vs NBD1-F508del + chimera — quantification of the trans stabilizing effect.
- FRET or co-immunoprecipitation in cells: validation of the physical interaction in cellulo.

4.3 In vitro biophysical characterization

- Secondary structure: CD (circular dichroism) and FTIR — verification of the absence of pathological aggregation of the chimera.
- Conversion test: agitation at acidic pH (Ladner-Keay et al., 2014), proteinase K resistance, Thioflavin T binding — verification that the chimera does not adopt an aggregated conformation by itself.

4.4 Cell-based assays

- Co-expression of the chimera NBD1-wildtype-AGAAAAGA with CFTR-F508del in HEK293 cells (transient transfection, variable molar ratios).
- Measurement of CFTR-F508del half-life: cycloheximide chase + western blot (t = 0, 30, 60, 120 min) — comparison with and without chimera.
- Measurement of CFTR-F508del ubiquitination: immunoprecipitation + anti-ubiquitin western blot.
- Maturation analysis: detection of band C as an indicator of trafficking to the membrane.
- Controls: wild-type CFTR alone, CFTR-F508del alone, CFTR-F508del + NBD1 without motif, CFTR-F508del + chimera with mutated motif.

5. EXPECTED RESULTS AND RISK MANAGEMENT

Experiment	Expected result	Interpretation	Risk / Alternative
In vitro pull-down	Detectable interaction	The chimera recruits NBD1-F508del	If no interaction → modify insertion site
Co-IP with mutated motif	No interaction	Correction depends on the AGAAAAGA motif	If residual interaction → refine the mutant control
DSF with chimera	$\Delta T_m \geq 3^\circ\text{C}$ of NBD1-F508del	Trans stabilization confirmed	If $\Delta T_m < 3^\circ\text{C}$ → test other chimeric variants
Thioflavin T	Low or absent signal	Chimera is not aggregating	If strong signal → modify sequence or position of motif
CFTR-F508del half-life	+30% upon co-expression	Partial escape from ERAD	If < 30% → combine with pharmacological correctors
Ubiquitination	Reduced signal	Less recognized by RNF5/RNF185	If unchanged → verify that the interaction is established

Band C western	Detectable signal	Trafficking to the membrane restored	If absent → verify by surface biotinylation
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6. EXPECTED IMPACT

Beyond the proof of concept for F508del, this principle of conformational correction in trans by a prion-like template could be extended to other CFTR mutations presenting folding defects, as well as to other directly analogous conformational diseases such as alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (Z-AAT) or certain forms of transthyretin amyloidosis. In the longer term, and subject to validation of the principle, this type of approach could open exploratory perspectives in other pathologies linked to protein misfolding, such as certain neurodegenerative diseases (Parkinson's, Alzheimer's), where propagating a healthy conformation would represent a complete reversal of the current paradigm.

At the fundamental level, this work would contribute to establishing a new paradigm: therapeutic correction through conformational information in trans, distinct from classical pharmacological approaches and gene therapies, opening the way to a new class of biological correctors.

7. TIMELINE

Period	Objectives
Year 1 — S1	Structural analysis, chimera design, cloning
Year 1 — S2	Expression/purification in <i>E. coli</i> , preliminary pull-downs and DSF
Year 2	Full biophysical characterization (CD, FTIR, proteinase K, ThT, FRET)
Year 3 — S1	Cell-based assays: co-expression, half-life, ubiquitination
Year 3 — S2	Cell-based assays: maturation (band C), optimization of co-expression ratios
Year 4	Follow-up experiments (patch-clamp if results are promising), writing, defense

8. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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